

Research Article

Lymphatic filariasis in Some Wards in Bodinga Local Government Area of Sokoto State, Nigeria

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Abstract

*The National Lymphatic Filariasis Elimination Programme (NLFEP) is committed to eradicate the lymphatic filariasis (LF) from Nigeria. Succeeding in this programme requires the availability of information on the distribution and nature of the disease from different parts of the country. Unfortunately, this is still not readily available. In this light, epidemiological study was carried out in five (5) wards in Bodinga Local Government Area of Sokoto State using Onsite Filariasis IgG/IgM Combo Rapid Test specific for *Wuchereria bancrofti* and *Brugia malayi* and search for clinical manifestations (hydrocele and lymphoedema). Out of the Two Hundred and Twenty-nine (229) individuals analysed, twenty-three (23) tested positive and this represents a prevalence of 10.0%. Infection rate was highest in Bangi/Dagaba ward with 13.3%. The males were more infected than the females; however, the difference is not statistically significant ($P>0.05$). The age bracket 70 and above showed the highest rate of infection, 18.2%. The unmarried individuals were significantly more infected than the married ones ($P<0.05$). No clinical sign was observed in the study area. Mass drug administration is recommended for these wards since the prevalence rate is above 1% and this could enhance the achievement of the goal of eradicating the disease from the country.*

Keywords: NLFEP, *Wuchereria bancrofti*, Lymphatic filariasis and Bodinga

Introduction

Lymphatic filariasis (LF) is the infection of the lymphatic system by filarial worms. It is a mosquito-borne tropical disease caused by species of parasitic filarid nematode worms belonging to the family *Onchocercidae*. *W. bancrofti* accounts for 90% of the infection and it is the commonest in Africa (Roberts and Janovy, 2010). Currently, more than 1.4 billion people in 81 countries of the world are at risk with at least 128 million people of all ages and sexes affected (Amaechi *et al.*, 2013).

LF afflicts over 25 million men with genital disease and over 15 million people with lymphoedema. At least 40 million people are affected in Africa. Nigeria is the third most endemic country in the world after India and Indonesia with an infection estimate of 22.1%. Since the prevalence and intensity of the infection are linked to poverty, its elimination can contribute to achieving the United Nations Millennium Development Goals (Okon *et al.* 2010; Omudu and Ochoga, 2011, and World Health Organization - WHO, 2013).

The Federal Ministry of Health has reported that 66% of the Nigerian population are at risk of lymphatic filariasis (Federal Ministry of Health (2013). The National Lymphatic Filariasis Elimination Programme (NLFEP) established in 1997 with the mandate of eradicating the disease from Nigeria by the year 2015 (Anosike *et al.*, 2005) has been mapping and treating lymphatic filariasis in Plateau and Nasarawa States over the past decade with the assistance of the Carter Centre. Researches are also being conducted for scaling up interventions against the disease. NLFEP was merged with the National Onchocerciasis Control Programme (NOCP) in 2007, to carry out the implementation of the WHO MDA in areas co-endemic for lymphatic filariasis and onchocerciasis (Federal Ministry of Health, FMOH, 2009). The NLFEP did set the year 2015 to eliminate the disease in Nigeria (Amaechi *et al.*, 2013).

However, information on the geographical distribution of the disease in many parts of the country especially in Northwest Nigeria is still sketchy. Therefore, a study which seeks to unveil the infection status of the people in the study area for proper mapping, effective control and eradication of the disease will add to the existing epidemiological data.

Methodology

Study Area

Bodinga Local Government Area (LGA) is one of the twenty three (23) LGAs in Sokoto State, Nigeria, with an area of 564Km² and a population of 209,444 9(National Population Commission, 2012). It lies between latitude 12°52' and 12°88,' and longitude 5°10' and 5°17'. It is bordered by Wamako LGA to the North, Yabo LGA to the West, Dange-Shuni LGA to the East and Shagari and Turetta LGAs to the South. The LGA is made up of eleven (11) political wards with the highest population in Bodinga/Tauma ward which is the headquarters of the council. There is a small water body called Baja River that runs through some parts of the Local Government. The inhabitants are mainly peasant farmers and live in small farming settlements. This study focused on five political wards in this local government which are Badau/Darhela, Bangi/Dabaga, Danchadi, Kauran Miyo and Sifawa/Lukuyawa wards.

Figure 1: Map of Bodinga Local Government Area of Sokoto State

Ethical Clearance

Ethical clearance was sought through an introductory letter from the department of Biological Science, Usmanu Danfodiyo University to the Sokoto State Ministry for Local Government and Community Development which upon receipt sent an approval letter to the Chairman, Bodinga Local Government for his assistance and cooperation. A health official from the health department in the local government was thus assigned to assist in mobilizing the community heads and the villagers. Informed consent was sought from all the participants after the explanation of the procedures and the likely benefits of the study. This explanation was made in the local language. A total of 229 persons participated in the study.

Interviews using structured questionnaire was conducted with the willing individuals from the various wards. The participants gathered in a designated place within their respective ward headquarters. The questionnaires were coded according to the wards with provisions for such information as the age, sex, occupation and other demographic data of the participants.

Detection of Circulating Filarial Antibody

After collecting the demographic data the circulating antibody presence was then detected using the lateral flow chromatographic immunoassay (*Onsite* Filariasis IgG/IgM Combo Rapid Test – Serum/Plasma/Whole Blood; CTK Biotech, Inc. San Diego, CA, USA). The patient's left index finger was cleaned with methylated spirit and then punctured using a sterile lancet. Blood was collected in a capillary tube and then transferred to the sample well on the test cassette. One drop of sample diluent or buffer was immediately added and the time noted. The result of each test cassette was read in 15 minutes. The test cassette contains a built-in internal control feature, the C line. The C line develops after adding specimen and the sample diluent. A positive result was when either the G line or the M line or both G and M lines developed, in addition to the presence of the C line. The result is negative if only the C line appeared. A test result is invalid if the C line does not appear even though the G line, the M line or both M and G lines appeared. Test result with the individual's identification code was recorded on the participant's questionnaire sheet.

Search for Hydrocoele and Lymphoedema

Participants were asked to partially disrobe and the local government health officer and the attached unit technologist who were already trained on the diagnosis of the various manifestations of LF including hydrocoele and lymphoedema examined them.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was done using the SPSS version 16 software package (SPSS Inc, Chicago IL). The results obtained were presented in simple descriptive statistics. Chi-square analysis was employed to test the significance of the distribution. The significance level was maintained at 0.05.

Results

Of the 229 individuals examined, 23 were positive for circulating filarial antibody representing 10.0% prevalence (Table 1). Infection was highest in Bangi/Dagaba ward with 13.3% and Badau/Darhela ward was the least with 8.5% (Table 1). There was no association between the wards sampled and the prevalence of lymphatic filariasis ($P>0.05$).

The sex distribution of the infection showed that males were slightly more infected than the females with 10.1% while the females had a prevalence of 10.0%. The difference in the sex distribution of the infection was not significant ($P>0.05$). These are shown in Table 2.

The age bracket 70 and above showed the highest prevalence of 18.2%. This was followed by the age group 40-49, which showed a prevalence of 16.7%. The age group 30-39 showed the least prevalence, 2.9% (Table 3). There was no difference in the distribution of the infection in relation to age ($p>0.05$).

The unmarried individuals were significantly more infected than the married respondents ($P<0.05$) with a prevalence of 13.8 while the married respondents had 9.5% prevalence (Table 4). The farmers had the highest prevalence of 12.3% compared to civil servants (6.9%) and others (9.8%) (Table 5).

Table 1: Prevalence of lymphatic filariasis in five wards in Bodinga LGA, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Wards	No. Examined	No. Infected	Prevalence (%)
Badau/Darhela	47	4	8.5
Bangi/Dabaga	45	6	13.3
Danchadi	47	5	10.6
Kauran Miyo	45	4	8.9
Sifawa/Lukuyawa	45	4	8.9
TOTAL	229	23	10.0

Table 2: Prevalence of Lymphatic Filariasis by sex in five wards in Bodinga LGA, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Sex	No. Examined	No. Infected	Prevalence (%)
Male	109	11	10.1
Female	120	12	10.0
Total	229	23	10.0

Table 3: Prevalence of Lymphatic Filariasis in Relation to Age in Five Wards in Bodinga LGA, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Age Group	No. Examined	No. Infected	Prevalence (%)
10-19	24	3	12.5
20-29	24	2	8.3
30-39	38	1	2.6
40-49	36	6	16.7
50-59	54	5	9.3
60-70	42	4	9.5
Above 70	11	2	18.2
Total	229	23	10.0

Table 4: Prevalence of Lymphatic Filariasis by marital status in five wards in Bodinga LGA, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Marital Status	No. Examined	No. Infected	Prevalence (%)
Married	200	19	9.5
Single	29	4	13.8
Total	229	23	10.0

Table 5: Prevalence of lymphatic filariasis by occupation in five wards in Bodinga LGA, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Occupation	No. Examined	No. Infected	Prevalence (%)
Farming	65	8	12.3
Civil Servants	29	2	6.9
Trading	12	1	8.3
Others	123	12	9.8
Total	229	23	10.0

Discussion

The evaluation of lymphatic filariasis' burden in a community is a determinant factor for planning, implementing and assessment of intervention strategies. Sensitivity, specificity, and simplicity are the important issues considered in ensuring efficiency of screening in lymphatic filariasis. The assessment of field performance and field applicability of new diagnostic methods in Nigeria and Africa at large is an important step towards controlling the infection. The overall prevalence of filarial antibody in this study was 10.0% and it is similar to previous findings elsewhere in Nigeria. For instance, Akogun (1992) observed 10.8% prevalence for *Wuchereria bancrofti* in a survey of 9 villages along the Benue River valley in Mutum Biyu, old Gongola State, Nigeria. This prevalence is also much higher than the World Health Organization's threshold of 1% positivity for MDA in a given community (WHO, 1998). It is however low when compared with the findings of previous studies in Nigeria. For instance, Udonsi (1986) recorded 25.6% *W. bancrofti* prevalence in Niger Delta areas, South-south Nigeria; Agi and Ebenezer (2009) observed 28.8% prevalence in Niger Delta Area; Omudu and Ochoga (2011) observed 32.6% prevalence from a study in Benue State, Central Nigeria; Amaechi *et al.* (2013) recorded 30.00% prevalence from somewhere in Ebonyi State, southeast Nigeria and Okonofua *et al.* (2013) reported 21% prevalence from a study in Ogun State, southwest, Nigeria.

Prevalence was observed to vary between the communities in this study. The socioeconomic status and the local environmental conditions of the communities could be responsible for these variations. Similar observations have been made by Prakash *et al.* (2003), Anosike *et al.* (2005) and Okon *et al.* (2010). Elkanah *et al.* (2011) have observed that socio-economic status, local environmental condition of communities and absence of ecological conditions that favour the breeding of vectors of lymphatic filariasis can be responsible for variable levels of infection with the disease among communities.

Understanding differences in disease rates between men and women might be helpful in understanding the pathogenesis of the disease (Evans *et al.*, 1993). The result of the antibody test showed a slight difference between the sexes. Prevalence in males was higher than in females. This is consistent with most reports on lymphatic filariasis from other parts of Nigeria (Uttah *et al.*, 2004; Omudu and Okafor, 2008; Dogara *et al.*, 2012 and Amaechi *et al.*, 2013). The reason for this in this area may be because the women folks may not be as prone to exposure to mosquito bites as the males. For instance, in a typical Hausa society, women tend to cover their entire body and do not stay out-door as much as the men and this could reduce their exposure to the vector.

The prevalence of lymphatic filariasis in this study did not follow any pattern with age. Individuals within the age bracket 70 years and above recorded the highest prevalence. Although the difference in the prevalence among the age groups is not statistically significant, it agrees with age related findings from Nigeria and elsewhere (Udonsi, 1986; Meyrowitsch *et al.*, 1995, and Omudu and Okafor, 2008).

The study showed a significant difference in the distribution of the infection in relation to marital status ($P < 0.05$). The unmarried individuals were significantly more infected than the married respondents. No similar finding has been encountered. The reason for this could be due to the type of activities the unmarried individuals engaged in. Unmarried individuals can keep late outside at night thus get exposed to the bite of the vector which is a factor in infection with lymphatic filariasis.

The study also showed that occupation is a factor in lymphatic filariasis infection. The farmers were more infected than other areas of work. This could be due to their outdoor activities which tend to expose them to the vector. This finding is in consonance with that of Elkanah *et al.* (2011).

Conclusion

The results of this study show that lymphatic filariasis is endemic in the five communities studied in Bodinga LGA, Sokoto State, Nigeria and the prevalence which is well above the 1% threshold positivity for Mass Drug Administration (MDA) in a given community as specified by the World Health Organisation makes these wards qualify for MDA.

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